

Corporate Governance and Firm Value

Zulai Musa¹, Onipe Adabenege Yahaya²

^{1,2}Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy,
Kaduna, Nigeria zulai.musa@nda.edu.ng

Abstract

Using Generalized Method of Moments, this paper examines the role of corporate governance in the maximization of firm value across 134 listed firms in the Nigerian Exchange Main Board for ten years period (2013-2022). The data used in this study is panel data hand-picked from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms. Data processing is done with STATA 15.1. The results show that risk committee size, leverage, asset tangibility, profitability and firm size are have significant effects on firm value, while concentrated ownership, board size, audit committee size, remuneration committee size, audit quality and dividend yield have no significant effects on firm value. These findings are useful to regulators, shareholders, creditors, market participants, and managers. The study is limited by the number of samples, specifically 134 firms. It is expected that further research can cover all the 156 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange. Further research is expected to add other corporate governance characteristics that have proved to be influential.

Keywords

Asset tangibility, big4, board committees, board of directors, corporate governance, dividend policy, external auditors, firm value; firm size, leverage, ownership structure; profitability

I. Introduction

A company's value is what is useful to stakeholders. This figure is reflected in the share price of the firm. It emanates from the forces of demand and supply of the capital market. It is a reflection of the stakeholders' perception of the firm's value. Firm value is essentially an important figure that stakeholders should pay attention to, because the value of a firm is a reflection of the financial conditions of the firm. It determines whether the firm is in good financial condition or not and whether it can generate wealth for stakeholders. In the case where firm value is high, stakeholders would be able to trust the firm and reward the firm by investing their equity and debt capital in the firm. In the final analysis, stakeholders' confidence could be the most effective instrument to enhance a firm's share price. On the other hand, if a firm's value is low, stakeholders would hesitate to invest their capital. This scenario would no doubt signal the decline in share prices, so that the value of the firm would also decline. Therefore, it is necessary to examine the determinants of firm value.

These determinants are ownership concentration, board size, board committees sizes, and external auditors (big4 or not). Ownership concentration is a proxy for ownership structure. Board size is a proxy for board of directors. Board committees' sizes refer to audit committee size, nomination committee size, remuneration committee size and risk committee size. The big4 is used to proxy external auditors. On the roles of control variables in enhancing firm value; dividend policy, firm size, asset tangibility, profitability, and leverage are used. For example, a higher leverage could lead the company to generate less cash; and less liquidity is likely to affect financial performance. Firms with high debt or leverage tend to hold their profits and prioritize the fulfillment of debt obligations. The greater the leverage of a firm, the more likely it would pay lower dividends in order to reduce dependence on outside capitals.

In contemporary years, firm value (FV) has become an important issue in the developing history of the business globe. The concept arises from stakeholders' expectations about their investments. This growing interest stems from Goldsmith era when investors deposit their Gold with the Goldsmith for a long time before asking for them; to the present, when economic added value is expected. Firm value is popularly represented by Tobin's Q (Awen et al., 2022; Cho, 1998; D'Amato & Falivena, 2020; Eberhart, 2012; Gharaibeh & Qader, 2017; Gosal et al., 2018; Ibrahim, 2017; Lamido et al., 2023; Mak & Kusnadi, 2005; Nguyen et al., 2015; Nguyen et al., 2016; Nguyen & Doan, 2020; Usman & Yahaya, 2023; Yahaya, 2022) and it is used in this study to proxy firm value.

Ownership structure of a firm can influence its value. Several scholars have connected ownership structure with firm value (Antwi et al., 2012; Cho, 1988; De Miguel et al., 2004; Ferina & Nurcahaya, 2014; Jentsch, 2019; Mishra & Kapil, 2017; Sualekhhattak & Hussain, 2017; Sulong & Nor, 2008; Vintila & Gherghina, 2015; Vo & Ellis, 2017). Also, the board of directors of a firm can influence its value. A number of scholars agree to this relationship (Carter et al., 2003; Eberhart, 2012; Fitri & Surjandari, 2022; Gosal et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2017; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Li et al., 2014; Sulong & Nor, 2008; Usman & Yahaya, 2023; Vintila & Gherghina, 2015).

The next factor that can affect the value of the firm is audit committee (Agyemang-Mintah & Schadewitz, 2018; Al-Matari et al., 2014; Bansal & Sharma, 2016; Felmania, 2014; Felo et al., 2003; Ferriswara et al., 2020; Gosal et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2017; Özcan, 2021; Submitter et al., 2020). Audit committee is one of the committees of the board of directors of a firm. It is one of the measures put in place to protect the investments of stakeholders in a firm. The audit committee plays a vital role in corporate governance because the committee holds the board and the organization accountable in almost every area, from internal and external audits to financial and risk management. An essential component of good corporate governance is the role of the audit committee. The role of audit committee is essentially to (1) recommend to the board of directors, audit firm for appointment (2) to oversight the functions of external auditor. The committee must monitor the process around financial reporting and the effectiveness of the company's internal controls. The committee must review the company's financial statements, and it must observe the independence of the external auditors. From the regulators' point of view, a good working audit committee indicates that the firm is in a good position, because it is likely to be able to fulfill its obligations to stakeholders in a timely manner. The firm's ability to meet its financial obligations in a timely manner means that the firm is sound and well managed.

The next factor that can affect the value of the firm is nomination committee (Agyemang-Mintah, 2015; Alhussayen & Shabou, 2016; Bel-Oms & Segarra-Moliner, 2022; Brick & Chidambaran, 2010; Eberhart, 2012; Mak & Kusnadi, 2005; Saibaba, 2013; Sulong & Nor, 2008; Suryaputri, 2023; Vintila & Gherghina, 2015). Nomination committee is probably the most important committee of the board because it nominates every person for appointment into the board and its several committees. It is one of the committees of the board of directors of a firm. A sound nomination committee of a firm is inseparable from how the board and its committees are effective and an effective board can lead a firm to high value. Firms with sound audit committee are more likely to do well and improve firm value. So highly effective nomination committee can improve financial performance, thereby leading to enhanced firm value. Nomination committee provides better board of directors' power and oversight and is more likely to produce better financial

performance, which may lead to enhanced firm value. Finally, a nomination committee is part of a firm's corporate governance mechanisms. A nomination committee evaluates a firm's board of directors and examines the skills and characteristics required of board candidates.

The next factor that can affect the value of the firm is remuneration committee (Agyemang-Mintah & Schadewitz, 2018; Al-Matari et al., 2014; Bansal & Sharma, 2016; Felmania, 2014; Felo et al., 2003; Ferriswara et al., 2020; Gosal et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2017; Özcan, 2021; Submitter et al., 2020). Remuneration committee is an important committee of the board because it rewards every person on the board of directors and its several committees. It is one of the committees of the board of directors of a firm. Therefore, a sound remuneration committee is inseparable from how the board and its committees are motivated to lead a firm to high value. A remuneration committee is a group of independent board members created to set the remuneration of senior-level employees, executives, and directors. This committee aims to ensure that the company's executive compensation is fair, competitive, and aligned with the organization's goal. Thus, an effective remuneration committee is synonymous with high financial performance, which can ultimately lead to high firm value.

The next factor that can affect the value of the firm is risk committee (Anton, 2018; Eberhart, 2012; Erin & Aribaba, 2021; Ferriswara et al., 2020; Gatzert & Martin, 2015; Gosal et al., 2018; Husaini & Saiful, 2018; Khan et al., 2017; Rao, 2018; Sulong & Nor, 2008). Risk committee is an important committee of the board because it helps to reduce exposure to risks by the firm, which ordinarily would have reduce the financial performance of the firm and thus reduces firm value. Therefore, a sound risk committee of a firm is a source for improvement in financial performance, which may lead to enhanced firm value. It is one of the committees of the board of directors of a firm. Therefore, a sound risk committee is inseparable from how the board and its committees are seen in terms of financial performance, which may lead to a high firm value. In essence, a firm risk committee's responsibilities include approval of applicable primary risk policies and review of certain associated frameworks, analysis and reporting established by management. The risk committee oversees reputational risks and conduct risks within its scope of its responsibility. Thus, an effective risk committee is synonymous with high financial performance, which can ultimately lead to high firm value.

The next factor that can affect the value of the firm is the kind of external auditors, whether, the audit firm is a member of big4 or not (Burnett et al., 2011; Eberhart, 2012; Feltham et al., 1991; Ferriswara et al., 2020; Ghosh, 2007; Haa & Minhb, 2020; Khan et al., 2017; Li & McConomy, 1999; Suffian et al., 2015; Vintilă et al., 2015). Big4 means that the audit firm is a member of PWC, KPMG, Deloitte, and Ernst and Young. External auditors are a part of corporate governance mechanisms in to prevent agents (management) from taking advantage of the principals (shareholders) in what is largely known as agency theory. It is important mechanisms of corporate governance required by law (Companies and Allied Matters Act, 1990 as amended in 2004 and 2020). It helps to reduce exposure to all forms of malpractices ranging from financial statement frauds, earnings management, etc. External auditors conduct independent assessments of firms' financial statements and disclosures. They confirm that financial statements do not contain errors or fraudulent activities. Corporations engage external auditors to ensure financial statements and disclosures remain free of material misstatements. These functions, together reduce the risks faced by the firms, which, increases the value of the firms.

II. Review of Literature

Along with other corporate governance mechanisms, the ownership structure of a firm is important in consideration for improvement in firm value. In this regard, a number of empirical studies have examined the role of ownership structure in enhancing firm value. For example, Cho (1988) examines the relation among ownership structure, investment, and corporate value,

focusing on whether ownership structure affects investment. Ordinary least squares regression results suggest that ownership structure affects investment and, therefore, corporate value. The evidence shows that ownership structure affects firm value. De Miguel et al. (2004) provide new evidence on the way in which ownership structure influences firm value. The empirical evidence ownership concentration model supports not only the monitoring but also the expropriation effects on firm value. Additionally, the insider ownership model provides results that confirm the convergence-of-interest and the entrenchment effects, even though Spanish insiders get entrenched at higher ownership levels than their U.S. and U.K. counterparts.

Sulong and Nor (2008) examine the effects of types of ownership structure on Malaysian firm's value using sample of 406 listed firms on the Main Board of Bursa Malaysia for the years 2002 and 2005. Government ownership indicates significantly positive relationship. In addition, foreign ownership has a negative significant relationship to firm value. Ownership concentration and managerial ownership provide insignificant effect to firm value. Ferina and Nurcahaya (2014) identify the influence of ownership structure on firm value of 32 listed firms from Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2009 – 2011. The results show that the ownership structure significantly influences the firms value: (1) the managerial ownership does not have a positive influence on firm value, (2) the institutional ownership has a positive and significant influence on firm value, (3) the foreign ownership has a positive and significant influence on firm value, (4) the concentrated ownership does not have a positive influence on firm value.

Vintila and Gherghina (2015) examine the influence of ownership structure on firm value in Bucharest Stock Exchange listed companies for over the period 2007-2011. Thus, after the econometric estimations using panel data regression models, they conclude a negative influence of insider shareholdings and employees' organizations ownership on firm value. However, the results showed a lack of association between State shareholdings and firm value. Sualekhkhattak and Hussain (2017) explore empirically the association between ownership structure and firm value. To obtain the correct empirical results, the study applies the correlation analysis technique, ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis on 148 non-financial companies listed on Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE), for the period of five years (2011-2015). Using t-test and panel data regressions, the study finds significant positive relationship between ownership concentration and firm value.

Mishra and Kapil (2017) explore the relationship of promoter ownership with firm value for Indian companies. Corporate governance structures of 391 Indian companies out of CRISIL NSE Index 500 companies listed on National Stock Exchange have been studied for their impact on performance of companies. Panel data regression methodology has been used on data for five financial years from 2010 to 2014 for the selected companies. Firm value measure considered is Tobin's Q. The empirical findings indicate that Tobin's Q is more impacted by ownership structure. There is significant positive association between promoter ownership and firm value. It is also indicated that the relationship between promoter ownership and firm value is different at different levels of promoter ownership.

Jentsch (2019) provides empirical evidence on the effectiveness of ownership structure on firm value. The empirical analysis conducted in the work is based on a panel data set consisting of 43 large public companies over a time frame of 6 years in the context of the small and open economy of Switzerland. The results of this analysis suggest that the presence of a controlling shareholder decreases firm value and that the presence of institutional investors as significant shareholders may also decrease value. Thus, the authors hypothesize that:

H₁: Ownership structure has no significant effect on firm value.

Board of directors of a firm has the ability to influence a firm value through oversight functions on the CEO. A number of empirical works have accepted that there is a nexus between the board of directors and firm value. For example, Carter et al. (2003) examine the relationship between board diversity and firm value for *Fortune* 1000 firms. After

controlling for size, industry, and other corporate governance measures, they find significant positive relationships between the fraction of women or minorities on the board and firm value. They also find that the proportion of women and minorities on boards increases with firm size and board size, but decreases as the number of insiders increases.

Sulong and Nor (2008) examine the effects of board governance on Malaysian firm's value using sample of 406 listed firms on the Main Board of Bursa Malaysia for the years 2002 and 2005. Overall, findings from this paper reveal that board governance; particularly board independence and board size can enhance firm value. Vintila and Gherghina (2013) examine the influence and causal relationship between board of directors' independence, CEO duality, and firm value. By estimating multivariate regression models for panel data, unbalanced, for a sample of companies listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange, the results show a positive influence of the percentage of independent directors on firm value.

Vintilă et al. (2015) investigate the influence of characteristics of the corporate board on firm value, using a sample of companies listed on the Bucharest Stock Exchange from 2007 to 2011. They find evidence that board size negatively influences firm value, whereas curvilinear relationships are found among board independence, diversity, and firm value. Kumar and Singh (2013) examine the effect of corporate board size on firm value for selected Indian companies. The study analyses the corporate governance structure of 176 Indian firms listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange using linear regression analysis. The empirical findings show a negative relationship of board size with firm value.

Khan et al. (2017) investigate the impact of corporate governance on firm value measured by Tobin's Q. Different corporate governance proxies i.e. board size, board independence and audit committee are interacted with firm value. A sample of 91 nonfinancial firms listed on KSE was selected over the period 2010-2014. The findings of the study show that board size has negative impact on firm value. Moreover, non-executive directors and audit committee have positive and significant impacts on firm value.

Gosal et al. (2018) determine the effects of Independent Board of Commissioners in increasing the firm value of 8 firms among listed firms on the IDX30 index within 2013-2017 period. Findings indicate that the Independent Board of Commissioners and Audit Committee have no influence on firm value significantly. Fitri and Surjandari (2022) examine the influence of Boards of Directors on Firm Value. This study uses secondary data from the IDX website. The population of this quantitative study is the annual report of Property and Real Estate companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2017 to 2020. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the data. The results of the study prove that the existence of independent commissioners has a significant influence on firm value. The proportion of women on the board has no influence on firm value. The education level of the board of directors has no influence on the firm value. Thus, the authors hypothesize that:

H₂: Board of directors' size has no significant effect on firm value.

Audit committee of the board of directors of a firm has the ability to influence a firm value through oversight functions and advice. A number of empirical works have accepted that there is a nexus between the audit committee and firm value. For example, Felmania (2014) identifies the influence of audit committee on firm value of 33 firms listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2010-2011. The research results show that audit committee has a positive and insignificant influence towards firm value. Khan et al. (2017) investigate the impact of audit committee on firm value of 91 nonfinancial firms listed on KSE was selected over the period 2010-2014. The findings of the study show that audit committee has positive and significant impact on firm value. Gosal et al. (2018) determine the effects of audit committee in increasing the firm value of 8 firms among listed firms on the IDX30 index within 2013-2017 period. Findings indicate that audit committee has no significant influence on firm value. Ozcan (2021) analyzes the impacts of audit committee on firm value of 141 manufacturing firms whose shares are traded on Borsa Istanbul during the period between 2011 and 2019. The paper finds that the inclusion of audit committee members with accounting and finance background, audit committee size and the number of

audit committee meetings positively influence firm value. Fitri and Surjandari (2022) examine the influence of Boards of Directors on Firm Value. This study uses secondary data from the IDX website. The population of this quantitative study is the annual report of Property and Real Estate companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2017 to 2020. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the data. The results of the study prove that the existence of independent commissioners has a significant influence on firm value, audit committee has a significant influence on firm value. Thus:

H₃: Audit committee size has no significant effect on firm value.

Nomination committee of the board of directors of a firm has the ability to influence a firm value through oversight functions. A number of empirical works have accepted that there is a nexus between the nomination committee and firm value. For example, Agyemang-Mintah (2015) looks at the relationship between nomination committee and firm value of firms among United Kingdom financial institutions. The result indicates a positive and statistically significant association between the nomination committee of a firm and its market value. Suryaputri (2023) examines how much influence board committees have on firm value of 13 Islamic Commercial Banks in Indonesia in 2017-2021. The results show that the Audit Committee and Risk Management Committee have significant effects on firm value. Meanwhile, Remuneration and Nomination Committee have no effect on company value. Thus, the authors hypothesize that:

H₄: Nomination committee size has no significant effect on firm value.

H₅: Remuneration committee size has no significant effect on firm value.

H₆: Risk committee size has no significant effect on firm value.

External auditors of a firm has the ability to influence a firm value through statutory audits. A number of empirical works have accepted that there is a nexus between the audit firm and firm value. For example, Debby et al. (2014) analyze the effect of audit committee and company's characteristics (size and return on equity) to Tobin's Q as firm value measurement. The sample which is used in this research banking companies listed at Indonesian Stock Exchange on period of 2008-2010. The result indicates that audit committee has negatively effect firm's value. Secondly, 1) Size has positively effects firm's value, (2) profitability has positively effects firm's value. Izukwe and Jeroh (2022) assess the statistical association between the qualities of auditors and the value of Nigerian listed companies of 22 Nigerian service listed companies for 2011 to 2020. According to the study's statistical findings, audit fees and firm value are significantly correlated; while audit tenure and joint audit have a negligible impact on firm value. The study finds that the characteristics of auditors as a whole have a considerable impact on the value of listed service firms in Nigeria. Thus, the authors hypothesize that:

H₇: Auditors' characteristic has no significant effect on firm value.

III. Research Method

The type of data in this study is secondary data from the Nigerian Exchange web site (<https://ngxgroup.com/exchange/trade/equities/listed-companies/>). The data in this study were taken from 134 companies listed on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange. The observation period is ten years, namely 2013-2022.

Table 1. Research Sample Criteria

No.	Information	Amount
1	All companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange for the 2013-2022 period.	156
2	Companies that are listed on the Main board of the Nigerian Exchange	(134)
Number of companies that are excluded		22
Research years		10
Number of observations		1,340

Source: Authors (2023)

The dependent variable in this study is firm value (TOBIN'S Q) and the independent variable is corporate governance (concentrated ownership structure, board of directors' size, board committees and auditors' quality (big4). This study has control variables, among others, namely, leverage, asset tangibility, profitability, dividend yield, and firm size. Measurements on each of the variables used are in Table 2. The full model of the study is as follows:

$$FV_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 COS_{i,t} + \beta_2 BS_{i,t} + \beta_3 ACS_{i,t} + \beta_4 NCS_{i,t} + \beta_5 RCS_{i,t} + \beta_6 RICS_{i,t} + \beta_7 AQ_{i,t} + \beta_8 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_9 ATG_{i,t} + \beta_{10} PROF_{i,t} + \beta_{11} DY_{i,t} + \beta_{12} FS_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

FV = Firm value (Tobin's Q)

COS = Concentrated ownership structure

BS = Board size

ACS = Audit committee size

NCS = Nomination committee size

RCS = Remuneration committee size

RICS = Risk committee size

AQ = Audit quality (Big4)

LEV = Leverage, ATG = Asset tangibility, PROF = Profitability (ROA)

DY = Dividend yield, FS = Firm size

Table 2. Operationalization of Variables Measurement

Variables	Definition	Measurement
FV	Firm value	Tobin's Q (This study reveals firm value as market value, because shareholders prosperity is influenced by firm value. In this study, firm value was measured using Tobin's Q)
COS	Concentrated ownership structure	Measured as the total number of block shareholders with 5% and above ownership
BS	Board size	Measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary
ACS	Audit committee size	Measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the audit committee
NCS	Nomination committee size	Measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the board nomination committee
RCS	Remuneration committee size	Measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the board remuneration committee
RICS	Risk committee size	Measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the risk committee
AQ	Audit quality	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise
LEV	Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total assets (%)
ATG	Asset tangibility	Measured as non-current asset divided by total asset (%)
PROF	Profitability	Measured as profit after tax divided by total asset (%)
DY	Dividend yield	Measured as cash dividend paid to profit after tax (%)
FS	Firm size	Natural logarithm of total assets

α = Constant
 β = Coefficient
 e = Error

Thus, our a priori expectations are stated as follow:

Whereas:

$X_1 > 0$: A rise in concentrated ownership will lead to increase in firm value;

$X_2 > 0$: A rise in board size will lead to increase in firm value;

$X_3 > 0$: A rise in audit committee size will lead to increase in firm value

$X_4 > 0$: A rise in nomination committee size will lead to a corresponding rise in firm value

$X_5 > 0$: A rise in remuneration committee size will lead to a corresponding rise in firm value

$X_6 > 0$: A rise in risk committee size will lead to a corresponding rise in firm value

$X_7 > 0$: A change of external auditor to big4 will lead to a corresponding rise in firm value

IV. Result and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics is in Table 3 for the variables.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FV	1340	.924	.284	.08	2.55
COS	1340	29.373	24.226	0	89
BS	1340	13.739	3.174	5	21
ACS	1340	6.046	.403	4	9
NCS	1340	0	0	0	0
RCS	1340	1.629	1.951	0	7
RICS	1340	3.471	2.945	0	12
AQ	1340	.797	.403	0	1
LEV	1340	86.943	19.254	8.63	254.75
ATG	1340	3.757	1.87	.25	13.74
PROF	1340	1.374	2.94	-20.23	9.54
DY	1340	4.378	4.338	0	19.05
FS	1340	8.958	.463	8.03	10.77

The descriptive statistics in Table 3 for the variables show that the number of observations is 1,340 (134 firms multiplied by 10 years), the mean of firm value is .924; the mean of concentrated ownership is 29.373 percent; the mean of board size is approximately 14 members; the mean of audit committee size is 6 members; the mean of nomination committee size is 0, suggesting that all the 134 firms do not have nomination committee; the mean of remuneration committee size is approximately 2 members; the mean of risk committee size is 3 members; the mean of audit quality is .797. on the control variables, leverage shows a mean of about 87 percent; asset tangibility shows a mean of 3.757 points; profitability has a mean of 1.374 percent; dividend yield shows a mean of 4.378 percent' and firm size shows a mean of 8.958 points. In terms of standard deviation (spread), firm value is .284; concentrated ownership is 24.226 percent; board size is 3; audit committee size is .403; nomination committee size is 0; remuneration committee size is about 2; risk committee size is about 3; and audit quality is .403. On the control variables, leverage shows a standard deviation of 19 percent; asset tangibility is 1.87 points; profitability is 2.94 percent; dividend yield is 4.338 percent and firm size is .463 points.

Firm value has minimum and maximum means of .08 and 2.55 respectively. Concentrated ownership has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 89 percent, respectively. Board size has minimum and maximum means of 5 and 21 members, respectively, audit committee size has minimum and maximum means 4 and 9 members, respectively, nomination committee size has minimum and maximum means of 0 and 0, respectively. Furthermore, remuneration committee size has minimum and maximum means 0 and 7, respectively. Risk committee size has minimum and maximum means 0 and 12 members, respectively. Audit quality shows minimum and maximum means of 0 and 1, respectively. In terms of control variables, leverage has minimum and maximum means 8.63 and 254.75 percent, respectively. Asset tangibility has minimum and maximum means .25 and 13.74, respectively. Profitability has minimum and maximum means -20.23 and 9.54 percent, respectively. Dividend yield has minimum and maximum means 0 and 19.05 percent, respectively. Firm size has minimum and maximum means 8.03 and 10.77 points, respectively.

The Pearson correlation coefficient matrix is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the corporate governance variables and firm value. Table 4 is the results of this relationship.

Table 4. Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
(1) FV	1.000												
(2) COS	0.138 (0.088)	1.000											
(3) BS	-0.308* (0.000)	-0.090 (0.268)	1.000										
(4) ACS	0.039 (0.631)	0.188* (0.020)	0.045 (0.577)	1.000									
(5) NCS	(.)	(.)	(.)	(.)									
(6) RCS	0.102 (0.213)	0.109 (0.182)	-0.098 (0.232)	0.106 (0.195)	(.)	1.000							
(7) RICS	0.077 (0.344)	-0.085 (0.298)	-0.101 (0.212)	0.159* (0.049)	(.)	0.076 (0.355)	1.000						
(8) AQ	-0.156 (0.055)	0.359* (0.000)	-0.093 (0.253)	0.057 (0.481)	(.)	-0.240* (0.003)	-0.008 (0.924)	1.000					
(9) LEV	0.574* (0.000)	0.099 (0.222)	-0.217* (0.007)	-0.005 (0.952)	(.)	0.085 (0.299)	-0.023 (0.779)	-0.227* (0.005)	1.000				
(10) ATG	0.548* (0.000)	0.183* (0.024)	-0.152 (0.060)	-0.016 (0.847)	(.)	-0.013 (0.873)	-0.133 (0.102)	-0.207* (0.010)	0.425* (0.000)	1.000			
(11) PROF	-0.087 (0.283)	0.098 (0.230)	0.091 (0.261)	0.145 (0.074)	(.)	-0.063 (0.443)	-0.003 (0.970)	0.276* (0.001)	-0.344* (0.000)	-0.202* (0.012)	1.000		
(12) DY	-0.339* (0.000)	-0.182* (0.024)	0.222* (0.006)	0.038 (0.640)	(.)	0.054 (0.507)	0.038 (0.639)	0.005 (0.947)	-0.176* (0.029)	-0.350* (0.000)	0.144 (0.076)	1.000	
(13) FS	-0.495* (0.000)	-0.180* (0.026)	0.277* (0.001)	0.165* (0.041)	(.)	-0.045 (0.586)	0.241* (0.003)	0.105 (0.196)	-0.224* (0.005)	-0.597* (0.000)	0.168* (0.038)	0.539* (0.000)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

The Pearson correlation coefficient matrix is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the corporate governance mechanisms and firm value as contained in Table 4. The correlation matrix in Table 4 for the variables shows that the bivariate relationship between firm value and concentrated ownership is positive but not significant at 5 percent. However, board size is negative but significant. Audit committee size is positive but not significant. Nomination committee size is omitted from the matrix because none of the 134 firms have nomination committee. Remuneration committee size is positive but not significant. Risk committee size is positive but not significant. Auditor quality is negative but not significant. However, in terms of control variables, leverage is positive and significant. Asset tangibility is positive and significant. Profitability is negative but not significant. Dividend yield is negative but significant. Finally, firm size is negative but significant.

Furthermore, the Generalized Method of Moments' results for the model is reported in Table 5.

Number of parameters = 12

Number of moments = 12

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 1340

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Table 5. GMM Regression Results

FV	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
COS	-.0004415	.000737	-0.60	0.549	-.001886 .001003
BS	-.0073839	.004866	-1.52	0.129	-.0169211 .0021534
ACS	.034085	.025598	1.33	0.183	-.0160862 .0842562
RCS	.0060694	.0079521	0.76	0.445	-.0095164 .0216552
RICS	.0187004	.0060292	3.10	0.002	.0068835 .0305174
AQ	-.0044977	.0440724	-0.10	0.919	-.0908781 .0818827
LEV	.0065469	.0007841	8.35	0.000	.0050101 .0080836
ATG	.033262	.013275	2.51	0.012	.0072435 .0592805
PROF	.0177097	.0090185	1.96	0.050	.0000338 .0353856
DY	-.0027843	.0031215	-0.89	0.372	-.0089023 .0033338
FS	-.1998906	.0668942	-2.99	0.003	-.3310007 -.0687804
/b0	1.848564	.6142692	3.01	0.003	.6446181 3.052509

In terms of significant effects or not, as it can be clearly seen from the results in Table 5, concentrated ownership, board size, audit committee size, remuneration committee size, audit quality, and dividend yield are not significant. However, risk committee size, leverage, asset tangibility, profitability and firm size are significant. In terms of beta coefficients, a unit rise in concentrated ownership leads to a little reduction (.04415%) in firm value. Similarly, a unit rise in board size, leads to a reduction in firm value by 0.73839 points. However, a unit rise in audit committee size leads to 3.4085 percent in firm value. Similarly, a unit rise in remuneration committee size leads to .60694 percent in firm value. In contrast, a unit rise in risk committee size leads to a significant and positive rise in firm value by 1.87 percent. However, a unit shift in big4 leads to reduction in firm value by .44977 percent. On the control variables, a unit rise in leverage leads to a rise in firm value by .65469 percent. On asset tangibility, a unit rise leads to 3.3262 percent in firm value. On profitability, a unit rise in profitability leads to 1.77 percent rise in firm value. On dividend yield, a unit pay rise in dividend yield leads to a reduction in firm value by .2784 percent. Finally, unit expansion of firm size leads to reduction in firm value by .19989 points. These results are mixed: some are consistent with our a priori expectations and some are not. Furthermore, some of these results are consistent with our previously reviewed empirical studies. However, some of the results are not consistent with past studies.

4.2 Hypothesis testing

The results of the first hypothesis of this study are based on the output coefficient and the p-value results in Table 5, which can be interpreted that the resulting p-value is greater than 0.05 is 0.5493, and the path coefficient value is $-.0004415$, which means that concentrated ownership has no significant effect on firm value. From this, it can be concluded that concentrated ownership is not a determinant indicator that affects the value of the firm. This is because concentrated ownership is not one of the requirements of regulators during the ten years observation periods. Thus, Hypothesis 1 is hereby accepted. Furthermore, the results of the second hypothesis in this study are based on the results of beta coefficient and the p-value in Table 5, which can be explained that the resulting p-value is 0.129 and the coefficient value is $-.007389$, which means that board size has no significant effect on firm value. These results indicate that board size is not one of the determinants of firm value. Thus, regulators and management should not waste time and money on the regulation of corporate board size.

The results of the third hypothesis in this study are based on the results of the output path coefficient and p-value in Table 5. It is explained that the resulting p-value is 0.183 and the path coefficient value is 0.034085, which means that audit committee size does not affect firm value. These findings of this study are indication that audit committee size does not provide additional motivation for companies to secure improved financial performance which may lead to improved firm value. In addition, the results of the fifth hypothesis of this study are based on the results of the output coefficient and p-value in Table 5, which can be explained by a p-value of 0.445 and a path coefficient of $.0060694$, which means that remuneration committee size does not contribute to firm value. These results of this study indicate that it does not matter to have concentrated ownership in terms of maximizing firm value.

The results of the sixth hypothesis of this study are based on the results of the output coefficient and p-value in Table 5, which can be explained by a p-value of 0.002 and a path coefficient of $.0187004$, which means that risk committee size contributes to firm value. These results of this study indicate that it matters to note risk committee size, most of business activities are faced with varies of risks. Finally, the results of the seventh hypothesis of this study are based on the results of the output coefficient and p-value in Table 5, which can be explained by a p-value of 0.919 and a path coefficient of $-.0044977$, which means that big4 auditors or non-big4 auditors are not important determinant in enhancing firm value.

V. Conclusion

This study aims to identify the effect of corporate governance on firm value. In accordance with the results, it can be concluded that concentrated ownership has no effect on firm value. This result may be because core ownership is not a requirement by regulators in publicly listed firms in Nigeria. Furthermore, board size is not a determinant of firm value. This shows that indeed companies with large board sizes may suffer from inability to take advantage of economies of scale and scope, thus, leading to poor financial performance which may lead to fall in firm value. In the same vein, audit committee size is not a determinant of firm value. This result shows that audit committee effectiveness is more important than size of the committee. The same result applies to remuneration committee size. This result is in line with motivation theories that argue that humans are insatiable; that when one level of need is met, another one emerges. In contrast, risk committee size is a determinant of firm value, according to the results in Table 5. This result is highly important to stakeholders since business are faced with series of risks.

Furthermore, the nature of auditors does not determine firm value. It means that changing audit firm from big4 to non-big4 or vice versa does not influence firm value. This result is good news for local audit firms and the development of the country in this regard. On the control variables, leverage, asset tangibility, profitability and firm size are determinants of firm value. However, dividend yield is not a determinant of firm value. Despite these results, the paper adds to the emerging body of literature on corporate governance and firm value relationship in Nigerian context using a reasonably wider data set.

The recommendations of this research for the firms are that (1) there should be no regulation for concentrated ownership since it is not significant (2) regulation on board size is not necessary, it is decision that firms can make (3) audit committee size should be preferred for audit committee independence or gender (4) remuneration committee size should not be preferred to remuneration committee gender or independence (5) risk committee size should be enhanced as far as regulation allows (6) there is no need to discriminate in hiring external auditors, because there is no special advantage offered by the big4 auditors. For further research, it is our hope that scholars can extend the research period and add other corporate governance variables such as foreign ownership, institutional ownership, managerial ownership, board independence, and board gender.

References

- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdulfatah, L. A., Yahaya, O. A., Agbi, S. E., & Mustapha, L. O. (2022). Mediating effect of firm value on the relationship between dividend payout and growth opportunities of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 14(2), 94-111.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Adamu, A., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Does board independence moderate the nexus involving ownership formation and financial performance? Evidence from Nigerian Exchange Group. *POLAC International Journal of Economic and Management Science*, 9(2), 1-9.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdullahi, M. (2023). Corporate governance committees and sustainability reporting of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (ISSN: 2454-6186)*, 7(7), 1761-1770.
- Abdulwahab, A. I., Bala, H., Yahaya, O. A., & Khatoon, G. (2023). Moderating effect of risk committee presence on the nexus between CEO characteristics and dividend policy: Evidence from listed companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(1), 165-176.
- Abubakar, A. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Board characteristics and financial performance. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Financial Studies*, 52, 7-19.
- Abubakar, B. A., Yahaya, O. A., & Nma, A. M. (2021). Board features and financial performance of Nigerian banks. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 10(1).
- Achraf, H., & Mohamed, N. S. (2022). The impact of Shariah Advisory Board characteristics on the financial performance of Islamic banks. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1), 1-38. doi: 10.1080/23322039.2022.2062911
- Adamu, D. A., & Saleh, M. (2020). Directors' remuneration and financial performance: Moderating role of board attributes of listed insurance companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Trade*, 5 (2), 23-34.
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.

- Ahmad, F. S. H., Yusuf, K., Ahmad, A. M. I., & Nazrul, H. A. R. (2017). Board attributes and performance of government-linked companies (glcs): Evidence from an emerging economy. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 14(3). doi: 10.22495/cocv14i3art8
- Ahmed, M., & Kehinde, S. O. (2022). Impact of Board Meeting and Board Size on Financial Performance of Listed Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria. *Bayero Business Review*, 6(2), 134-147.
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Ali, A., Nejia, N., & Abdelfettah, B. (2018). Chief Executive Officer attributes, board structures, gender diversity and firm performance among French CAC 40 listed firms. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 44, 218-226. doi: 10.1016/j.ribaf.2017.07.083
- Anissa, D. (2021). Does financial performance moderate the relationship between board attributes and corporate social responsibility in French firms? *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 12(4), 372-399. doi: 10.1108/JGR-02-2021-0016
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.
- Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.
- Augustine, O. O., & Juliet, C. U. (2022). Board Characteristics and Financial Performance of Conglomerates in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 7(2), 12-18. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24018/ejbmr.2022.7.2.1344>
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. In Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Gender and nationality among board members and audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.
- Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.
- Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.
- Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.
- Ayman, H. B. (2022). Audit committee attributes and financial performance of Saudi non-financial listed firms. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1), 3-13. doi: 10.1080/23322039.2022.212723
- Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.
- Balogun, J. E., Agbi, S. E., Yahaya, O. A., & Joshua, S. G. (2023). Institutional ownership and firm value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria: the moderating role of dividend payout. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 15(1), 85-111.
- Elamer, A. A., & Benyazid, I. (2018). The Impact of Risk Committee on Financial Performance of UK Financial Institutions. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 8(2), 161-180. doi: 10454/16621

<http://www.ijem.upm.edu.my/vol14no2/1.%20Moderating%20Effects>

- Ibrahim, M. F., Okika, N. P., Yunusa, I., & Janada, A. (2020). Risk Management Committee Size, Independence, Expertise and Financial Performance of Listed Insurance Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, IV(V), 313-319.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research (2602-3385)*, 3(12), 75-89.
- Kamaludin, K., Ibrahim, I., & Sundarasan, S. (2020). A Middle Eastern viewpoint on the moderating effects of family business on audit committee diligence and firm performance. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 14(2), 173-188. doi:
- Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.
- Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.
- Lateef, O. M., Saheed, Z. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2015). Institutional factors and personal tax compliance in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(24), 146-157.
- Mohammed, S. B., Ridzwana, M. S., Jalila, J., & Fakarudin, K. (2022). Moderating Role of Financial Performance on The Relationship Between Board Attributes and Corporate Sustainability Disclosure Compliance. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 16(3), 383-395.
- Monther, E., Mustafa, H., & Ainulashikin, M. (2022). Moderating role of Shariah committee quality on relationship between board of directors effectiveness and the performance of Malaysian Takaful. *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*. doi: 10.1108/CR-09-2021-0123
- Muhammad, A. N., Sun, X., & Ramiz, U. R. (2017). Board attributes and financial performance: The evidence from an emerging economy. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 51(3).
- Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Management and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- olufunmilayo, A. A., & Temiola, A. A. (2022). Effect of corporate tax on the relationship between capital structure and firm value of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *NDA journal of management sciences research*, 2(ISSN:2795-2770), 90-99.
- Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.
- Samaijala, N., Sulieman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326
- Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.
- Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information

- disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female gender diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.
- Tnushi, P. T., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Ownership structure and dividend policy of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 10(1), 68-82.
- Umar, A. M., & Hussaini, B. (2020). Corporate Governance and Financial Performance of Nigeria Listed Banks. *Jour of Adv Research in Dynamical & Control Systems*, 12(1). doi: 10.5373/JARDCS/V12I1/20201002
- Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Business*, 8(1), 36-47.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Yahaya, O. A. & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improves intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Journal of Economic and Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency

- Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022h). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance and Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.

- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.
- Yahaya, O. A., Farouk, B. K. U., Lamidi, S. Y., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). Impact of competition on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(18), 52-61.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Ohiaka, I. Z., Ahmed, M. N., Mustapha, L. O., Jimoh, O. I., Onyabe, J. M. (2015). Principal components analysis of local government revenue in Nigeria: 1993–2014. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 5(10), 38-47.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *J. of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.
- Yakubu, I., Ahmed, M. N., Yahaya, O. A., & Agbi, S. E. (2023). Audit committee and audit report lag: moderating role of ownership concentration of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(7), 77-100.
- Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.
- Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International J. of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.